

Milestone:

M3.6 Phenotypic and clinical metadata framework. An agreed minimal phenotypic and clinical metadataset, a set of agreed quality parameters for the shared metadata

Lead Participant:

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Author:

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Due:

30 Nov 2022

Date Of Completion:

31-10-2023

Means of Verification

First version by means of D3.4 was published May 23 2022

Second version by means of D3.5 was published Jan 20 2023 and after EC review was asked to be revised.

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

Yes (final version Oct 2023) and No (first version was published in May 2022)

Final version of the phenotypic and clinical metadata framework is/was due in M36 (bad alignment with M3.6). Major delays were caused by lack of availability of (clinical domain) experts during SAR-Cov-2 and extensive requested review of D3.5

Project participants & others

See [Framework set up working document v1.1.docx - Google Documenten](#) as well as all related Zenodo publications

Next action steps

This framework document is/will be part of the 1+MG Framework and be used and updated within the GDI project (and resulting operational organisations)

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